

Measure or Not: Measured Skin Temperature vs Pre-Set Neutral Temperature for Thermal Feedback

Zidi Zhou¹[0009-0009-5554-5968] and Patrizia Di Campli San Vito¹[0000-0002-2499-8464]

University of Glasgow, Glasgow, G12 8RZ, United Kingdom
2545266z@student.gla.ac.uk
Patrizia.DiCampliSanVito@glasgow.ac.uk

Abstract. When presenting thermal stimuli, researchers typically adopt a pre-set neutral temperature as a baseline temperature, and make the temperature fluctuate upon it. This paper investigates the difference between using the measured skin temperature and a pre-set neutral temperature during a user study, exploring recognition rates and subjective ratings. Results suggest that a pre-set neutral temperature is sufficient for effective use of thermal cues, but adjusting to skin temperature could increase comfort.¹

Keywords: Thermal feedback · real-time skin temperature · haptic

1 Introduction

Most research into thermal feedback has used a *neutral temperature* as base temperature, which is kept and returned to when no active change is presented [5,1,4]. This approach guarantees that designed thermal changes can be experienced in the same way by everyone, as the skin will adapt to the pre-set neutral temperature and the same thermal changes will then be perceived. Jones et al. [2] suggested in their work that continuously measuring skin temperature was not necessary for detection of thermal changes, but have not shown any proof for this assumption. Peiris et al. [3] only used measured skin temperature as base line with high perception, but have not compared these results with pre-set neutral temperature cues.

Therefore, our experiment set out to compare recognition rate and comfort of thermal cues for a pre-set neutral temperature and measured skin temperature as base temperature. For recognition rate we found only minimal non-significant differences. Comfort ratings, however, showed that warm cues from a pre-set neutral temperature were rated as less comfortable than warm cues based on skin measurements. These results reinforce indications that the more complex set-up for continuous skin temperature measurement does not provide a substantial benefit to a thermal display regarding recognition rate, but could increase the comfort of warm stimuli.

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2 Experimental Design

The experiment was designed as a 2x2x2 within-subjects study, with independent variables *base temperature* (neutral/skin), *degree of change* (3°C/variable) and *direction of temperature change* (warm/cold). The experiment was divided into four rounds, covering all four combinations of base temperature and degree of change, with five warm and five cold cues randomly presented within each round. The rate of temperature change was 3°C/s, the base temperature 32°C, presented for 10s at the beginning of the rounds, adapted from previous work [5]. Thermal cues were presented for 5s in the 3°C conditions. In the varied degree of change condition, temperature was changed between 2°C and 7°C, and were either presented 4s or 5s, with base temperature between the cues varying between 2s and 8s, to counteract learning effects. Conditions were counterbalanced, but, one of the 3°C degree of change conditions was presented first throughout, as introduction to the feedback. Dependent variables in this user study were recognition rate and subjective ratings, collected in questionnaires after each round. The questionnaires consisted of 7-point Likert scales asking about the comfort of the thermal cues. A priori power analysis suggested that 10 participants would be sufficient to capture large effects.

10 (7 female, 3 male) undergraduate students (22-26y) took part in the study. The user study was conducted at the university library and took under 1h, no incentive was given. The design was approved through our institution's undergraduate Ethics board.

The experiment used an ASUS X50J laptop with a Quad Universal USB ThermoElectric Controller (built by SAMH Engineering) with two attached 1x1cm Peltier thermoelectric stimulators on heat-sinks and an Arduino Uno with attached Max6675 thermocouple sensor attached, controlled via Python.

Participants were presented with the information sheet and signed a consent form, then were first introduced to the thermal cues for familiarisation. Then the rounds of feedback were presented, each followed by the questionnaires to capture the subjective rating and provide a short break. During the rounds, participants were asked to report when they felt a temperature change and the experimenter logged these. After four rounds, participants were thanked and left.

3 Results

Repeated measures ANOVA found no significant differences for recognition for any factors. Statistical analysis for Comfort with a repeated measures ANOVA showed significant differences for the interaction between direction of temperature change and base temperature ($F(2)=6.080$, $p=0.01$, $\eta^2=0.076$) and for direction of temperature change alone ($F(2)=4.944$, $p=0.019$, $\eta^2=0.0137$), which will not be investigated by itself due to its part in the interaction. Post hoc tests with Bonferroni corrections showed significant differences between warm thermal changes between neutral and skin temperature ($t=-4.212$, $p=0.003$).

4 Discussion and Conclusions

Only small differences were found between the base temperature modes for recognition rate, none statistically significant. These results reinforce previous work [2] suggesting that a pre-set neutral temperature might be as useful as thermal cues based on measured skin-temperature, especially as we found no differences for detection between warm and cold stimuli, which others reported in their previous work [5]. Evaluation of the comfort ratings, however, showed differences: warm temperature changes based on the neutral temperature were rated significantly less comfortable than the warm cues based on skin temperature. Our results suggest that adjusting the base temperature might make warm cues more comfortable in thermal displays.

5 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange.

Our work has shown that comfort of warm thermal cues can be increased when starting from the skin temperature rather than a pre-set neutral base temperature. Overall, research has shown that warm thermal cues often are rated less comfortable than cold cues, yet affective associations often relate warm cues with positive emotions. We invite cognitive psychologists to discuss thermal perception and affective associations to increase feedback effectiveness.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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